

MATHEMATICS

APPLICATION OF INVARIANTS TO FIND ORBITS IS A FAMILY OF VECTOR FIELD

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Abstract

Maximum rank differential reflections are important in various areas of mathematics, especially Riemannian geometry. In Riemannian geometry, the concepts of immersion and submersion, which are used not only in geometry, but also in such sciences as mechanics, theoretical physics, and the theory of relativity, play an important role. In this paper it is studied the second order differential invariants of submersions with respect to the group of motions of a Riemannian manifold. The smooth Riemannian manifold of dimension with a metric tensor, a family of smooth vector fields defined on the manifold. A family can contain a finite or infinite number of smooth vector fields. It is clear that the orbit is a smooth curve (one-dimensional manifold), if D consists of one vector field.

In this part, we study the geometry of the singular foliation generated by the orbits of smooth vector fields.

If the dimensions of the leaves of a foliation with singularities are the same, then it is a regular foliation in the sense of the definition given in [3]. G. Sussman and P. Stefan showed that the decomposition of a manifold into orbits is a singular foliation [5-7]. Numerous studies have been devoted to the study of the geometry of the singular foliation [1-7].

Keywords: Vector fields, orbits, differential invariant, infinitesimal generator, invariant function, flow.

Definition 1. The orbit $L(x)$ of a family D of vector fields, passing through a point x from M , is defined as the set of such points y from M , for which there are real numbers $t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k$ and vector fields $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_k$ from D (where k is an arbitrary natural number) such that

$$y = X_k^{t_k}(X_{k-1}^{t_{k-1}}(\dots(X_1^{t_1}(x))\dots)).$$

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Definition 2. Let G the group of transformations, acting on the manifold M . A subset $N \subset M$ is called G invariant, and a group G is called a subset symmetry group N , if for any $x \in N$ and $g \in G$, $g \cdot x \in N$.

Definition 3. Let G the group of transformations, acting on the manifold M . A function $F: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called an invariant function of the transformation group if for all $x \in M$ and all $g \in G$, $F(g \cdot x) = F(x)$.

The following theorem is known [2].

Theorem-1. Let a group G act on a manifold M and $F: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a smooth function. Then F is an invariant function if and only if each level set $\{x \in M: F(x) = c, c \in \mathbb{R}\}$ is an invariant G subset of the manifold M .

Let G the k -dimensional Lie group of transformations. Then it has k infinitesimal generators (vector fields). The following theorem is known [2].

Theorem-2. A function $F(x)$ is G group invariant if and only if it satisfies the equation $X(F) = 0$ for every infinitesimal generator X of the group G .

In space $R^3 \setminus \{x = 0\} \setminus \{y = 0\}$ let's look following vector fields:

$$X_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \frac{y}{x^2 + y^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \quad X_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z}$$

Finding the flow of the vector field $X_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \frac{y}{x^2 + y^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z}$:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = 1 \\ \dot{y} = 0 \\ \dot{z} = \frac{y}{x^2 + y^2} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

From here we get:

$$x = t + x_0$$

$$y = y_0$$

We put these equalities to the last equation of system (1) and obtain the following equation

$$\dot{z} = \frac{y_0}{(t + x_0)^2 + y_0^2}$$

We integrate and find

$$dz = \frac{y_0 dt}{(t + x_0)^2 + y_0^2}$$

$$\int dz = -\int \frac{x_0 dt}{x_0^2 + (y_0 + t)^2} = \int -\frac{x_0^2 d \frac{y_0 + t}{x_0}}{x_0^2 \left(1 + \frac{y_0 + t}{x_0}\right)^2} = -\operatorname{arctg} \frac{y_0 + t}{x_0} + c$$

$$z = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{t + x_0}{y_0} + c$$

According to the initial condition $z(0) = z_0$ find

$$z_0 = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x_0}{y_0} + c$$

$$z = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{t + x_0}{y_0} + z_0 - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x_0}{y_0}$$

Mean vector field flow X_1 has the following form

$$X_1^t(x, y, z) = (t + x, y, \operatorname{arctg} \frac{t+x}{y} + z - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{y}) \text{ or } X_1^t(x, y, z) = (t + x, y, \operatorname{arctg} \frac{t+y}{x^2 y^2 + xt} + z)$$

Vector field flow X_1 generates a one-parameter group $\{X_1^t\}$.

Now we find the flow of the vector field

$$X_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} - \frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial z}$$

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = 0 \\ \dot{y} = 1 \\ \dot{z} = -\frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} \end{cases} \Rightarrow x = x_0$$

$$y = y_0 + s$$

$$\dot{z} = -\frac{x_0}{x_0^2 + (y_0 + s)^2}$$

Solving the differential equation

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = -\frac{x_0}{x_0^2 + (y_0 + s)^2}$$

find

$$\int dz = -\int \frac{x_0 ds}{x_0^2 + (y_0 + s)^2} = \int -\frac{x_0^2 d \frac{y_0 + s}{x_0}}{x_0^2 \left(1 + \frac{y_0 + s}{x_0}\right)^2} = -\operatorname{arctg} \frac{y_0 + s}{x_0} + c$$

$$z = -\operatorname{arctg} \frac{y_0 + s}{x_0} + c$$

According to the initial condition $z(0) = z_0$ we have the following equalities

$$c = z_0 + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{y_0}{x_0}$$

$$z = z_0 + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{y_0}{x_0} - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{y_0 + s}{x_0} = z_0 + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{-x_0 s}{x_0^2 + y_0^2 + y_0 s}$$

So the flow of the vector field X_2 has the following form

$$X_2^s(x, y, z) = \left(x, y + s, z - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{-xs}{x^2 + y^2 + ys}\right)$$

The flow of vector field X_2 generates a one-parameter group $\{X_2^s\}$.

We find the invariant function of the vector field X_1

$$\frac{dx}{1} = \frac{dy}{0} = \frac{dz}{\frac{y}{x^2 + y^2}}$$

From here we find, that the function $I_1 = y$ is an invariant of the one-parameter group $\{X_1^t\}$, generated by the flow of the vector field X_1 .

Solving the equation:

$$\frac{y dx}{x^2 + y^2} = dz, \Rightarrow \frac{y^2 d \frac{x}{y}}{x^2 + y^2} = \frac{d \frac{x}{y}}{\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)^2 + 1} = dz, \Rightarrow z = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{y}$$

find another invariant function $I_2 = z - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{y}$.

Vector field X_2 express in terms of functions $I_1 = y$ u $I_2 = z - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{y}$.

$$\dot{I}_1 = \dot{y} = 1, \dot{I}_2 = \dot{z} - \left(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{y}\right) = -\frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{x^2}{y^2}} \left(\frac{x}{y}\right) \dot{x} - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{x^2}{y^2}} \left(-\frac{x}{y^2}\right) \dot{y} = -\frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} - 0 + \frac{x}{x^2 + y^2} = 0$$

To mean $X_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial I_1}$. The invariant function of this vector field is I_2 .

The result. From this we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem-3. In space $R^3 \setminus \{x = 0\} \setminus \{y = 0\}$ orbit of a family of vector fields $D = \{X_1, X_2\}$ generates a singular foliation whose leaves are a family of helicoids:

$$L_c = \{(x, y, z) : z - \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{y} = c\}.$$

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